

ISic1386

Greek funerary inscription for Aischylos son of Chryson

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

unknown

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Described by Gualtherus (1624) as coming from the ruins popularly identified with the shrine of the god Hadranus (not identified). All later editions derive from Gualtherus.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

The stone is one of three described as 'petra nigra' by Gualtherus (1624: 50), but neither state of conservation nor dimensions are recorded.

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

Text is recorded over two lines without comment.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No information recorded

Letter heights:

Line 1: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. Ἀχίσχυλος
2. Χρύσωνλος

Apparatus

Text derived from Gualtherus

Gualtherus: ΧΙΣΧΥΛΟΣ

Gualtherus: ΧΡΥΣΩΛΟΣ

Translation (en)

Aischylos, son of Chryson

Commentary

The inscription was, according to Gualtherus, in the possession of Rochus Marullus, doctor of law; it has not been seen since Gualtherus. The name Aischylos [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V3a-37195>] is common and well attested in Sicily (10 instances) and elsewhere (c.250 instances); but the name Chryson [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V3a-41662>] is rare, with only 5 recorded instances, and this the only one from Sicily (see LGPN vol. 3A).

Digital identifiers:

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PHI 140893

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1386>

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